
IMPACT OF HRM PRACTICES ON EMPLOYEE JOB SATISFACTION: A CASE STUDY OF SELECTED PRIVATE COMMERCIAL BANKS IN CAMBODIA

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Abstract: In addition to its immeasurable contribution to achieving goals of the organization, Human Resource Practices (HRM) practices are considered to be a method of encouraging employees' satisfaction with their jobs. The question has always been whether HRM practices have a significant and positive effect on employee job performance. Actually, they are intended to improve employees' attitudes which will in turn improve their performance. There has also been the issue of whether employee commitment and satisfaction significantly affect organizational performance. This has aroused the necessity to determine the positive, strong relationship between HRM practices and employee satisfaction. Undoubtedly, HRM practices, if applied effectively, can increase employee satisfaction and commitment, and resultantly generate a positive impact on organizational performance. An observable fact is the existence of three significant factors or a cycle of interaction between and among HRM practices, job satisfaction and organizational commitment. It reveals that HR policies and practices are likely to raise the level of job satisfaction among employees, which ultimately helps employees to develop more commitment to their organization.

The purpose of the study is to investigate the influence of HRM practices on employees' job satisfaction. To conduct this research, 80 respondents, randomly selected from 20 private commercial banks in Phnom Penh City, Cambodia were surveyed conveniently through a structured questionnaire. The responses were then analysed by conducting a test of hypothesis, correlation and regression analysis using SPSS software. From the findings, correlation analysis shows that Human Resource Management practices have a significant relationship with job satisfaction. Moreover, regression analysis reveals that the five factors of HRM practices depicted in the model explains about 57.3 percent of job satisfaction among the bank employees and supports the fact that there is a positive influence on their job satisfaction. The survey also found that work-life balance practices (WLBP), compensation and reward (CNR), recruitment and selection (RNS) have the most influence on job satisfaction (JS). As a result, the findings of this study will provide new insights to the bank managers concerning the approaches to guarantee job satisfaction among employees and consequently boost their commitment and overall performance.

Keywords: Human Resource Practices, Employees' Job Satisfaction, Work-Life Balance Practices, Compensation and Reward, Recruitment and Selection, HR Practices.

1. Introduction: The proliferation of private commercial banks by the government in the Kingdom of Cambodia in recent times has made this sector highly competitive and challenging more than ever before. Banks are known to be labour-intensive service organization and as such must optimize the utilization of its human resources to effectively tackle the impending challenges. In that regard, the increased endorsement demands that banks in Cambodia should aim to secure a sustainable competitive position in the market. As a result of this rapid growth in the banking sector, there has been a significant increase in the demand for efficient and experienced human resources in the execution of their multiple demanding services in the business industry. Two vital aspects related to Human Resource Management is in the area of recruitment and retention of employees. The attraction of new competent workforce and retention of the existing talented personnel calls for sound administrative policy, consistent Human Resource practices, employee job satisfaction and organizational commitment; these are highly imperative (Ahmad & Schroeder 2003; Khera 2010; Mohammad 2004;

Mizan et al. 2013). In this dispensation, every bank should concentrate on sound HR practices to ensure the motivation and job satisfaction of its employees. The impact of Human Resources Management (HRM) practices popularly known as HR Practices on organizational performance and employee attitudes has been a prominent area of research in the developed countries for years (Delaney and Huselid, 1996; Huselid, 1995; Katou and Budhwar, 2007; Petrescu and Simmons, 2008). However, it is surprising that a few studies have been conducted on HR Practices in the context of developing countries in general (Schuler as cited in Budhwar and Debrah, 2001; Sing, 2004; Yeganeh and Su, 2008).

In any market-oriented economy, the banking sector plays an essential role in rendering financial services and serving as an intermediary between savers and investors. It plays a primary role in allocating credits by relative risk and return to efficient economic agents. A sound banking sector generally contributes to the smooth operation of the economy and promotes economic welfare of the society. Cambodia was transformed from a mono-banking system into a two-tier banking system in 1989. This resulted to changes in central planning economy to market economy. The proliferation of banks during this period no doubt left Cambodia with an excessively large number of banks relative to its size and rate of development. Despite that, Cambodia still has one of the lowest rates of banking intermediation in the world. There is still the attempt to find a key challenge and option for further reform toward safety net and sound banking system in Cambodia. The entire burden falls on the recruitment and retention of competent human resources equipped with the skills to tackle the enormous economic task.

This study has been conducted to analyse the influence of HR practices on employee job satisfaction in the context of Cambodian private commercial banks. Practitioners, researchers, academicians, policy makers, local and foreign entrepreneurs operating in Cambodia and other developing countries could benefit from this study by exploring the association between HR practices and job satisfaction. This study will enhance the contemporary research and practice of human resource management. Furthermore, it would also be helpful for the developed countries as they find developing countries (like Cambodia) an attractive place for investment due to the rapid development of their emerging markets, cheap and skilled and unskilled workforces among other necessities.

Figure 1: Banking System in Cambodia
Source: Phillip Bank Cambodia

2. Research Objectives: The cardinal objective of the study is to address the influence of HRM practices on employee job satisfaction.

Other specific purposes are:

- To determine the degree of association between HRM practices and job satisfaction.
- To offer some recommendations and policy measures regarding the pattern of HRM practices that will increase high employee job satisfaction for the selected private commercial banks.

3. Methodology:

3.1. Research Design: The design employed in this study was exploratory research. This type of study, which is exploratory in nature, involves a valuable way of finding out what is happening; to seek new insight; to ask questions and to assess phenomenon in a new light, (Robson, 2002). It investigates research questions that have not been studied in depth. The preliminary results often lay the groundwork for future analysis. The questions in explanatory research tend to start with “why” or “how”, with the goal to explain why or how a previously studied phenomenon takes place.

3.2 Sample Design: There are 59 private commercial banks in Phnom Penh City, Cambodia as at 31 December 2022. In this research, 20 out of these commercial banks, were randomly selected. This constituted 34% of the population. Respondents that were randomly drawn from the selected banks were interviewed as per their respective convenience.

3.3. Sources of Data and Methods of Data Collection: Both primary and secondary data were used in the study. Personal interviews through a structured questionnaire were conducted to collect primary data from 60 employees of the banks (i.e., three employees from each of the twenty banks). Secondary data were collected from various articles and books relevant to the study. A five-point Likert scale from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5) was used to measure the variables of HRM practices and job satisfaction.

3.4. Reliability and Validity of the Scale: Reliability and Validity of the Scale was used to measure the consistency of results the scale would produce if the test had been administered repeatedly. This is vital to understand the validity of the scale used to analyse the data. Cronbach’s Alpha, which is the most widely used method, was used to test the reliability of the scale. It is pertinent to note that its value ranges from 0 to 1 but the satisfactory value is required to be more than 0.6 for the scale to be reliable (Malhotra, 2002; Cronbach, 1951). Therefore, Cronbach’s alpha scale was used in this study to ascertain and determine the reliability.

Table 1: Reliability Value of the Scale

Scale	No. of Items	Cronbach’s Alpha (α)
Recruitment and Selection	10	.625
Training and Development	12	.621
Performance Appraisal	10	.706
Compensation and Reward	9	.652
Work-Life Balances	11	.701
Job Satisfaction	20	.834

As shown in Table 1 above, the estimated reliability value is between Cronbach’s Alpha $\alpha = 0.621$ to 0.834 all through the scales. Therefore, it can be said, that the scales used are adequately reliable because all the Cronbach’s alpha (α) reliability values are higher than the standard alpha value of 0.6. The questionnaire was validated by seeking the advice of several experts who affirmed that the face and content validity of the questionnaire was adequate.

3.5. Research Hypothesis: In this research, the following hypotheses had been developed.

Hypothesis 1: H1: HRM practices have a significant relationship with job satisfaction.

Hypothesis 2: H2: HRM practices have a significant influence on job satisfaction.

Hypothesis 3: H3: Recruitment and selection have a positive influence on job satisfaction.

Hypothesis 4: H4: Training and development positively influence job satisfaction.

Hypothesis 5: H5: Performance analysis positively influences job satisfaction.

Hypothesis 6: H6: Compensation and reward positively influence job satisfaction.
 Hypothesis 7: H7: Work-life balance practices positively influence job satisfaction.

4. Data Analysis and Findings:

4.1 Test of Hypotheses: SPSS version 20 was used to conduct the test of the hypotheses by using correlation and multiple regression analysis, ANOVA and t statistics coefficient table. The findings of the study are presented and discussed below.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix for HRM practices and Job Satisfaction

Variables	RNS	TND	PA	CNR	WLBP	JS
RNS	1					
TND	0.482** (0.000)	1				
PA	0.349** (0.001)	0.566** (0.000)	1			
CNR	0.321** (0.004)	0.484** (0.000)	0.230* (0.040)	1		
WLBP	0.298** (0.007)	0.422** (0.000)	0.308** (0.005)	0.246* (0.028)	1	
JS	0.490** (0.000)	0.547** (0.000)	0.417** (0.000)	0.531** (0.000)	0.582** (0.000)	1

$$JS = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 RNS + \beta_2 TND + \beta_3 PA + \beta_4 CNR + \beta_5 WLBP \tag{i}$$

The fitted Regression Model is:

$$JS = -2.113 + .201(RNS) + .075(TND) + .116 (CBPA) + .310(CNR) + .379 (WLBP) \tag{ii}$$

Here, α_0 = Constant

TND = Training and Development

Dependent Variables:

- PA = Performance Appraisal
- JS = Job Satisfaction
- CNR = Compensation and Reward

Independent Variables:

- WLBP = Work-life Balance Practices
- RNS = Recruitment and Selection

Table 3: Predictors of Job Satisfaction - Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²
1	0.75(a)	0.573	0.544

Predictors: (Constant) RNS, TND, PA CNR and WLBP.

The Standardized Regression Model is presented above. As shown in Table 2, all the HRM practices RNS, TND, PA, CNR, WLBP are independently and positively correlated with JS at 1% levels which denotes highly significant. Hence, Hypothesis 1 of the present study has been accepted. In this presentation, it is evident that the maximum correlation ($r = 0.582$) existed between WLBP and JS, followed by TND and JS ($r = 0.547$), CNR and JS ($r = 0.531$). Obviously, more emphasis should be given to WLBP for indicating the highest degree of job satisfaction of employees. Training and development and compensation and rewards are also very crucial for ensuring high employee job satisfaction. In spite of the fact that the difference between RNS and JS (0.490) and PA and JS (0.417) is not so significant, these are also necessary for job satisfaction. It is also established that HRM practices occur in pairs and positively correlated with one to another and also statistically significant at 1% - 5% level. The

relationship between PA and TND ($r = 0.566$) is the highest followed by CNR and TND ($r = 0.484$) among the five HRM practices.

4.2 Regression Analysis: A multiple regression analysis was performed to find out the predictors of job satisfaction as conceptualized in the model. Table 3 and 4 show the summery measure and ANOVA of the model and table 5 shows the coefficient for the predictors of JS.

Table 4: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	2941.139	5	588.228	19.847	.000b
	Residual	2193.248	74	29.638		
	Total	5134.388	79			

a. Dependent Variable: Job satisfaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), RNS, TND, PA CNR and WLBP

The HRM practices (RNS, TND, PA CNR and WLBP) in the above model articulated the ability to predict job satisfaction ($R^2 = 0.573$). In this model the value of R^2 indicates that 57.3% of the observed variability in the job satisfaction can be explained by HRM practices specifically, RNS, TND, PA CNR and WLBP. The remaining 43.7% of the variance is not explained by these variables which mean that the rest 43.7% of the variation in job satisfaction is related to other variables which are not depicted in the model. This variance is highly significant as indicated by the F value in the ANOVA table-4 ($F = 19.847$ and $P = 0.00$).

Table 5: Coefficients for Predictors of JS

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	-2.113	6.524		-.324	.747
	RNS	.580	.254	.201	2.280	.025
	TND	.172	.254	.075	.679	.499
	PA	.297	.239	.116	1.244	.217
	CNR	.983	.279	.310	3.530	.001
	WLBP	.697	.156	.379	4.466	.000

Dependent Variable: Job satisfaction

Source: Survey data

From table 5, we can see that, all the HRM practices (RNS, TND, PA CNR and WLBP) are positively influencing job satisfaction of employees. Particularly WLBP, CNR and RNS respectively have the most significant influence on employee's job satisfaction since the value of (t for WLBP is 4.466, $p = 0.00$, $df = 74$) for CNR value of ($t = 3.530$, $p = 0.001$, $df = 74$) for RNS value of ($t = 2.280$, $p = 0.025$, $df = 74$) and PA (value of $t = 1.244$, $p = 0.217$, $df = 74$) and TND (value of $t = 0.679$, $p = 0.499$, $df = 74$) have moderate influence on employee job satisfaction. Thus, all the hypotheses 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7 are accepted.

5. Discussion

5.1. Human Resource Management: Simply put, Human Resource Management (HRM) is the practice of recruiting, hiring, deploying and managing an organization's employees. It deals with the people dimensions in the organization especially HR planning, job analysis, recruitment and selection, orientation, compensation, performance appraisal, training and development and labour relations (Dessler, 2013). According to (Senyucel, 2009), HRM comprises a blend of people-centred management practices that recognizes employees as assets and geared to creating and maintaining skilled and committed workforces for achieving organizational goals. Ultimately, HRM is strategic approach to nurturing and supporting employees and ensuring a positive workplace environment.

5.2. Job Satisfaction: Job satisfaction (JS) basically refers to the state of well-being and happiness of a person concerning performance in the workspace and its environment. It is “a positive or pleasing emotional state resulting from the evaluation of a person’s job” (Locke, 1976, p.1304). Job satisfaction is a general attitude of employees either favourable or unfavourable towards their job. Some studies have shown a positive relationship between job satisfaction and job performance (Judge et al., 2001). Therefore, one may rightly assume that customer satisfaction is a direct function of employee satisfaction and vice versa.

5.3. HRM Practices and Job Satisfaction: HRM practices are considered to be a method of encouraging employees' satisfaction with their jobs, and these practices have proved to proffer a significant and positive effect on employee job performance. Several studies have been carried out on HR practices and job satisfaction, and it is assumed, that there is a close relationship between Human Resource (HR) and Job Satisfaction (JS). Many researchers have demonstrated that sound HRM practices resulted in better job satisfaction which ultimately improves organizational performance. According to Lamba and Choudhay (2013), HRM practices provide an edge to enhance employee's commitment towards achievement of a firm's goal in the global competitive market. Based on the findings, the study concluded that HRM practices such as training and development, compensation and welfare measures have a significant impact on organizational commitment and are associated with blue-chip organizational performance; this also helps in the retention of knowledgeable and skilled employees.

In order to provide a greater insight, (Majumder, 2012) conducted a study into the current HRM practices i.e., recruitment and selection, compensation package, job security, career growth, training and development, management style, job design and responsibility, reward and motivation and working environment and their impact on employee's job satisfaction on private banking sector. The study revealed that most of the employees are dissatisfied with the compensation package followed by reward and motivation, career growth, training and development, management style, and job design and responsibilities. In their research, (Goyal and Shrivastava, 2012) found that appropriate HR practices of an organization can improve the job satisfaction level of the employees and strengthen their commitment towards their organization. Furthermore, (Martin, 2011) conducted a study to determine the influence of HRM practices on job satisfaction, organizational commitment and intention to quit. He focused on basic HRM practices including recruitment and hiring, compensation and benefits, training and development, and supervision and evaluation. The result of the study revealed a significant relationship between perceptions of respondents on HR practices and intention to quit, mediated by organizational commitment and job satisfaction. Moreover, (Absar, Azim, Balasundaram and Akhter, 2010) found that human resource planning (HRP), training and development (TND) have a positive impact on job satisfaction (JS). They also found that TND has the most impact on JS. Another expert, (Gurbuz, 2009) investigated and concluded that proposed practices which comprised participation, empowerment, job rotation, self-directed work teams, and contingent compensation had a positive correlation with employee's job satisfaction. Also, (Aswathappa, 2008) was of the opinion that an organization should have sophisticated HR plans to motivate its employees. Sound HR planning can enhance job satisfaction of employees by providing opportunities for employees to participate in planning their careers (Weeratunga, 2003). From the above empirical literature, it has been confirmed that there exists significant relation of employee satisfaction and productivity with HRM practices. Based on this, organizations, especially service-oriented ones such as banking organizations should focus on proper HR practices to satisfy and motivate their employees and gain competitive advantages over their rivals.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations:

6.1: Conclusion: In consideration of the findings from correlation and regression analysis regarding the association and impact of HRM practices on job satisfaction of private commercial banks' employees operating in Cambodia, it has been found that all the factors of HRM practices covered in this study are positively and significantly associated with employee job satisfaction and also predict about 57.3% level of job satisfaction. It has also been observed that, work-life balance practices (WLBP), compensation

and reward (CNR), training and development (TND) and recruitment and selection (RNS) have the highest degree of association and influence on employee job satisfaction.

6.2 Recommendations: The researcher therefore recommends that to ensure the job satisfaction of employees and thereby to boost their commitment and performance, banks should emphasize more on the implementation of these HRM practices. Especially, banks should put arrangements in place to balance employees' work and family responsibilities. The banks should adopt some welfare measures like health care, food aid, stress management and counselling. They should offer attractive and competitive compensation packages to their employees. Rewards and incentives should be fairly distributed while training and development opportunities should not only be lacking but also be adequate. The career plan of banking institutions should be growth oriented and recruitment and selection process should be dispassionate, unbiased and strictly based on merit.

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